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Groundwater Vulnerability Mapping Of Hydrocarbon Spilled Areas Around OML 30 Oil Field In Delta State Using Drastic Method

Onavwie U.A.^{1*}, Jegede S.I.³ and Omajene A.³

Physics Department, College of Education Warri, Nigeria^{1,3}

Physics Department, Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma, Nigeria²

*Email: onavwie.ufuoma@coewarri.edu.ng/ GSM: 08035809532

ABSTRACT

This research was carried out to determine the aquifer vulnerability of the groundwater in the Hydrocarbon Spilled areas around OML 30 Oil Field in Erhoike-Kokori in Delta State, using the DRASTIC technique. The Geophysical data were collected using the Abem SAS 1000 Terrameter adopting the Schlumberger array for the Vertical Electric Sounding (VES). The Resistivity models obtained correlated well with the physicochemical characteristics. The Depth to water table, Aquifer media, Soil media, Impact on Vadose, and Hydraulic Conductivity were calculated and deduced from the geophysical data collected during the field work. The Topography of the study Area was mapped using the Geographic Positioning System (GPS). It was found that, the study area has a high net recharge of groundwater and is low to moderately vulnerable to contamination with vulnerability index ranging from 125.5 to 130. The pH, TDS, Iron and Maganese concentration in all the surface water and the total dissolved solids (TDS) ranges from 5.30-127.20 mg/L, the pH ranges from 4.8-6.00 mg/L, the Fe ranges from 0.423-1.357mg/L while Mg, Ni, Cr, Pb, Cd and Si are <0.001 in all the five water samples. Au ranges from 0.015-0.113 mg/L, Cu ranges from 0.037mg/L to 0.076 mg/L.; however, samples of groundwater from the study area falls within the WHO permissible limit. This hydrological result confirmed the DRASTIC result of the area. This is as result of the hydrogeological and geological setting of the area. The soil in the study area has good sorption that prevent direct infiltration of contaminants into the aquifer. The application of the (GIS) to produce the DRASTIC model map was found to be a suitable tool for analyzing the groundwater vulnerability in the study area.

Keywords: Vertical Electrical Sounding, hydrological, DRASTIC model.

INTRODUCTION

Groundwater is difficult to manage due to often limited understanding of the groundwater systems; uncertainties in monitoring of its status; poorly defined flow boundaries; transboundary issues; poor abstraction management; uncertainty in groundwater, surface water inter-connections and often a poorly defined regulatory structure [1].

Recently, land use types have been integrated into the DRASTIC framework to account for the influence of human activities [2]. Human activities are increasingly being recognized by scholars as a factor influencing the probability of groundwater contamination [3]. Consequently, examining the spatiotemporal dynamics of various land use types and integrating them as an additional factor in

groundwater vulnerability assessments can enhance the accuracy of identifying regions at risk of contamination [4].

Research has demonstrated a strong correlation between land use types and human activities. With the continuous development of urbanization, urban construction areas have expanded and human activities such as mining and industrial production have exerted certain impacts on the natural environment, leading to various forms of environmental pollution [3]. These include an increased risk of urban flooding [4], higher greenhouse gas emissions [5], and greater discharge of industrial pollutants [6]. Groundwater vulnerability assessment aims to protect this critical resource by identifying areas at risk of contamination and informing sustainable management practices [8] & [9]. The fundamental principle of such assessments is to classify areas into different vulnerability categories, which helps pinpoint the key factors contributing to groundwater pollution [10]. Providing vulnerability maps based on these assessments supports evidence-based decision-making and represents a crucial step toward sustainable groundwater and environmental management [10].

. In areas where economic development is prioritized, the shifts in land use patterns are especially pronounced, leading to various ecological and environmental challenges, with notable impacts on groundwater vulnerability, and consequently, on groundwater quality [11].

Different types of land use changes, including industrialization, urbanization, agricultural practices, and deforestation, have adverse effects on groundwater quality [12].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study methods involved both the invasive and non-invasive method of investigation. The non-invasive method involved two phases of measurements, the hydro-geologic and geophysical measurement. While Geographic Information Science (GIS) was used to generate the geospatial distribution of the DRASTIC model's parameters for easy vulnerability study of the area. The invasive method involved the collection of water samples from open streams, hand dug wells and boreholes for geochemical laboratory analysis to validate DRASTIC model which is the non-invasive results.

Location Of The Study Area

The map shown in figure 1 is a generalized map of the study area which is a sub-urban area showing the outline of Erhoike-Kokori Inland where OML 30 Oil field is located in Delta State and is characterized by a lot of Oil exploration and exploitation activities as shown in figure 2 with forty six oil wells drilled and operational with a flow station and gas flaring site as shown in figure 2 formerly owned by Shell petroleum Development Company (SPDC) but now owned by the Nigeria Petroleum Development Company (NPDC). Figure 2 shows the polluted environment as a result of possible equipment failure due to aging pipelines or probably pipeline or oil facility vandalization. The study area is located in the South-South zone of Nigeria, and lies within latitudes $5^{\circ} 39'01.5''$ and $5^{\circ} 38'45.5''$ N and Longitude $6^{\circ} 04'09.2''$ and $6^{\circ} 04' 01.9''$ E.

Figure 1. Map of the study Area (Erhoike-Kokori Inland) (Generated from Google maps)

Figure 2: Polluted environment as a result of Gas flaring at Erhoike-Kokori (Photo by Onavwie Ufuoma).

Fig. 3. Schlumberger array

Considering a Schlumberger electrode arrangement as shown in Figure 3, the outer electrodes A and B are referred to as current electrodes while the inner electrodes M and N are the potential electrodes. Therefore, from the equation:

$$V=IR \quad (1)$$

[From Ohm's law in Electricity]

$$R = \frac{\rho L}{A} \quad (2)$$

$$\rho_a = K.R \quad (3)$$

Where: $K = \pi(a^2 - b^2) / b$ Schlumberger array

$a = \frac{AB}{2}$ (half-current separation distance) value in metre, $b = \frac{MN}{2}$ (half-voltage separation distance) value in meter, k= geometric factor.

V=voltage, I=current, R=Resistance, L=Length, A=Cross-sectional Area.

Model Field Data Presentation

Table 1: Field resistivity result for VES 1

S/NO.	AB/2	MN/2	RESISTIVITY(Ω m)
1	1	0.5	418.64
2	2	0.5	534.58
3	5	1	381.89
4	10	2	473.79
5	15	2	661.25
6	20	5	729.35
7	25	5	734.68
8	30	5	625.99
9	50	5	607.5
10	60	5	654.33
11	80	5	477.57
12	100	5	400.08

Table 2: Field resistivity result for VES 2

S/NO	AB/2	MN/2	RESISTIVITY(Ω m)
1	1	0.5	910.09
2	2	0.5	991.57
3	5	1	322.53
4	10	2	217.32
5	15	2	382.3
6	20	5	487.71
7	25	5	300.08
8	30	5	385.54
9	50	5	685.68
10	60	5	1463.1
11	80	5	20186
12	100	5	16051

The Result of the Inversion Model for the Vertical Electrical Sounding Curves given in figures 5 & 5

DISCUSSION OF THE PARAMETERS OF THE DRASTIC METHOD

In the DRASTIC method, spatial datasets on **D**epth to groundwater, **R**echarge by rainfall, **A**quifer type, **S**oil properties, **T**opography, **I**mpact of the vadose zone and the aquifer's hydraulic **C**onductivity are combined [13]. DRASTIC is an acronym name for the above seven parameters considered in this method. Each of the aforementioned hydrogeology factors was assigned a rating from 1 to 10 based on a range of values. The ratings are then multiplied by a relative weight ranging from 1 to 5. Weights reflect the relative importance of each parameter in contributing to the overall objective. The most significant factors have a weight of 5 while the least significant ones have a weight of 1.

Depth to Groundwater (D)

It represents the depth of material from the ground surface to the water table through which a contaminant travels before reaching the aquifer. The shallower the water depth, the more vulnerable the aquifer is to

pollution and vice versa. The results of groundwater depth was derived from Vertical Electric Sounding (VES) Interpretation carried out in the study area. Figure 6 below showed that depth to water table ranges from 18m to 40m. To the far North has the deepest water table about 40 m and the range of water table towards North East water table ranges from 30- 40m. Also, Towards North central, the depth to water table dropped compared to the extreme North and it ranges from 25-33m. Towards the south, southeast and south the depth to water table is shallowest, it ranges from 18 - 24m.

Figure 6: Spatial Results of Depth to Water Table for Erhoike-Kokori in Delta State

Net Recharge (R)

It represents the total quantity of water that reaches the water table (figure 7). Recharge is the principal factor for leaching and transporting contaminants. The more the recharge is, the more vulnerable the aquifer is. Net recharge of the study area was inferred from the Geology of the area being sandstone which belongs to Benin Formation It has average values ranging from 100 to 160 mm/year and is uniform for the study area.

Figure 7: Spatial Results of Net Recharge for Erhoike-Kokori in Delta State

Aquifer Media (A)

This factor refers to the rate at which the aquifer is replenished (figure 8). In those rocks with inter-granular porosity, or secondary (inter-granular dissolution and dolomitization in carbonate rocks), the dispersive component is controlled by the size and lithology [14]. The larger the grain size is, the more fractures or openings within the aquifer are, the higher the permeability and thus vulnerability of the aquifer. Figure 8 revealed that the aquifer media of the aquiferous unit that underlies the study area is friable sandstone and clayey consolidated sandstone and the weight was found to be 3 and rate was 8.

Figure 8: Spatial Results of Aquifer Media for Erhoike-Kokori in Delta State

Soil Media (S)

It is the upper weathered zone of ground surface. Consequently, sandy soils are assigned a higher rating than clay soils. Soil has a significant impact on the amount of recharge that can be infiltrated into the ground and hence has the ability of a contaminant to move vertically into the vadose zone and revealed to be 2 based on the geology of the study area that is made up of the Benin Formation and basically loamy soil. The weight to be 2 and rate to be 6

Topography (T)

It refers to the slope (Figure 9) of the land surface. Topography indicates whether a pollutant will runoff or remain long enough to infiltrate. Where slopes are high, there is high runoff, thus aquifer vulnerability. When slopes are under 2%, the velocity of direct runoff is quite small, thus favouring infiltration and evapotranspiration [15]. The GPS data which was used to generate a topo map of the study area and three point from the north to east to the central (3 points method), From Figure 9, the topography was found to be between 0-3 and the weight is 1 and the rating was 10.

Figure 9 Spatial Results of Topography for Erhoike-Kokori in Delta State

Impact of the Vadose Zone (I)

It refers to the unsaturated zone above the water table. Percolation of precipitation, air, and any kind of surface water occurs within this zone, so it has an important role in infiltrating the pollutant materials into the saturated zone the deeper the water table the lesser the effect of vadose zone on the aquifer and vice versa. For the study area weight was 5 and rating was 8 as the result of the analysis showed the area was made up of friable sandstone (Figure 9).

Hydraulic Conductivity (C)

It refers to the rate at which water flows horizontally through an aquifer and refers to the capability of the aquifer materials to transmit water. Hydraulic saturated zone, thus contaminant migration is limited depending on the permeability of the medium. The higher the conductivity is, the more vulnerable the aquifer [16] (Figure 10). Hydraulic conductivity of the study area was acquired by calculating it using the three points method. The GPS data was used to generate a topo map of the study area and three points from the north to east to the central (3 points) where VES results was acquired were used to form triangle, the depth to water table at that three points was noted and subtracting from the elevation, thereafter, equipotential lines were determined, from the equipotential lines, hydraulic head was identified and hydraulic gradient was computed. The hydraulic conductivity of the aquifer unit underlying the study area ranges from 0.95 to 1.9Gal/day (Figure 10). The weight was 3 and rating was 1.

Figure 10: Spatial Results of Hydraulic Conductivity for Erhoike-Kokori in Delta State

GOVERNING EQUATION FOR DRASTIC INDEX

$$D_{in} = D_w D_R + R_W R_R + A_W A_R + S_W S_R + T_W T_R + I_W I_R + C_W C_R \quad (4.1)$$

- D₁ = (5x1) + (4x6) + (8x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 118
- D₂ = (3x5) + (6x4) + (8x5) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 124
- D₃ = (2x5) + (4x6) + (8x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 123
- D₄ = (1x5) + (6x4) + (x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 118
- D₅ = (2x5) + (8x4) + (8x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 123
- D₆ = (3x5) + (6x4) + (8x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 124
- D₇ = (3x8) + (6x4) + (8x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 124
- D₈ = (4x5) + (6x4) + (8x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 133
- D₉ = (2x5) + (6x4) + (3x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 123
- D₁₀ = (2x5) + (6x4) + (8x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 123
- D₁₁ = (2x5) + (6x4) + (8x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 123
- D₁₂ = (4x5) + (6x4) + (8x3) + (6x2) + (10x1) + (8x5) + (1x3) = 133

PRESENTATION OF GEOCHEMICAL RESULTS

The result of Geochemical analysis of five water samples and two soil samples were collected in the study area for laboratory analysis and all the samples showed from that the total dissolved solids (TDS) ranges from 5.30-127.20mg/L (Table 3). the pH ranges from 4.8-6.00mg/L (Table 4). The Fe ranges from 0.423-1.357mg/L while Mg, Ni, Cr, Pb, Cd and Si are <0.001 in all the five water samples. Au ranges from 0.015-0.113mg/L, Cu ranges from 0.037mg/L to 0.076mg/L. Fiscal Coliform is untraceable in the five-

water sample. while the soil samples picked around VES 1 and VES 2 are insignificant <0.001mg/Kg while soil collected from VES1 & VES 2 has pH of 5mg/Kg (Table 3 and 4). The Fe concentrations in soil sample picked at, VES 1 & VES 2 are 34.24, 679.8 and 678.8 mg/L respectively. Au concentration in the three soil samples are 11.102mg/Kg, 10.162mg/Kg and 10.162mg/Kg respectively. The concentration of Pb, Cu, Cd, Si, Cr, and Ni is <0.001mg/Kg

Table 3: Physico-chemical Analysis of Water Samples Collected from the study Area

Parameters	Gas Flaring Site	Erhoike Stream Water	NPDC BH	Hospital Erhoike	VES 12 Hand dug Well	WHO (
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	
Lab Ref.No:	TNL/6103	TNL/6104	TNL/6105	TNL/6106	TNL/18/07	
Colour, Pt. Co	25	25	0	0	25	2.0
Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), mg/l	42.40	10.60	5.30	10.60	127.20	
Electrical Conductivity	80.00	20.00	10.00	20.00	240.00	
Ph	5.70	5.60	5.00	4.80	6.00	6.5-8.5
Alkalinity, mg/l	20.00	2.00	8.00	3.00	44.00	
Acidity	1.60	0.40	2.40	1.20	2.40	
Nitrate, mg/l	1.51	1.15	1.20	0.792	1.703	50
Carbonate, mg/l	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	
Sulphate, mg/l	1.25	0.97	0.44	0.36	2.78	
Iron, mg/l	1.357	1.122	0.520	0.423	0.454	
Manganese, mg/l	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.4
Magnesium, mg/l	1.347	0.849	0.317	0.965	2.477	
Sodium, mg/l	9.056	1.333	1.026	2.021	10.607	
Chloride, mg/l	7.09	3.56	1.56	3.56	17.73	
Potassium, mg/l	1.479	0.282	0.851	1.039	6.826	
Nickel, mg/l	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.07
Chromium, mg/l	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
Silver, mg/l	0.018	0.032	0.015	0.081	0.113	
Calcium, mg/l	4.001	2.001	1.001	1.001	<0.001	
Lead, mg/l	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.01
Copper, mg/l	0.076	0.051	0.047	0.065	0.037	2.0
Cadmium, mg/l	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
Silicon, mg/l	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
Faecal Coliform	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	

GROUNDWATER VULNERABILITY OF THE STUDY AREA

The vulnerability map generated by the GIS using DRASTIC parameters acquired from the geophysical, hydrogeological, and geological field data that were obtained from the study area showed that the aquifer that underlies the study area has heterogeneous sensitivity to contaminants infiltration into the aquifer in the area. The sensitivity of the area was cumulatively determined by the seven DRASTIC parameters by imputing them into the DRASTIC model to determine the vulnerability index of the area. The vulnerability index of the area ranges from 118 to 125 toward the extreme north, south-south, and south west as calculated using DRASTIC parameter (Figure 11). However, the lowest vulnerability index of the range occurs in the extreme north. This implies that the sensitivity of aquifer that underlies the northern part compared to the aquifers that underlie south-south and south west is very low. This indicates that the potential of aquifers in those areas to contaminants infiltration is low.

Figure 11: Vulnerability map of the study Area

Toward the eastern part of the north central and to east of the study area where red to yellowish red coloration dominant on the vulnerability map of the study area (Figure 11), the vulnerability index ranges from 125.5 to 130. These values indicate that those areas have moderate potential or sensitivity for contaminants infiltration into the aquifers that underlie the areas. The result of the geochemical analysis for the water samples collected in the study area corroborated the result of the DRASTIC index obtained from area. The result showed that groundwater from the aquifer that underlies the area does not have any trace of microorganism originating from fecal nor leachate. To further buttress the DRASTIC result obtained from the study area, the geochemical result of the soil samples in the study area where NPDC oil wells are located and there was oil spills in the area., the result has high concentrations of heavy metals; silver ranges from 10.162-11.102mg/kg, iron ranges from 34.25-679.80mg/kg, and manganese is 11.40mg/kg (Table 3 & 4).

These high concentrations of heavy metals give good indication of the effect of the oil spills on the surface; however, the concentration of water samples in the existing borehole in the study area show very low concentrations. These observations show that the aquifer protective capacity of the area does not permit easy infiltration of contaminant above into the aquifer. This low to moderate potential to vulnerability by the aquifer that underlies the study area is as a result of the geology of the area with good sedimentological properties that gives active filtration mechanism that can eliminate any contaminants in the surface from infiltrating into the aquifer despite the flat topography that exists in the area that favoured direct infiltration. Furthermore, the hydrogeological setting of the study area contributes to the protective mechanism the aquifer in the area enjoys. The aquifer parameters do not allow vertical permeability rather encourages horizontal permeability, thus preventing direct infiltration of contaminants from the surface into the aquifer.

CONCLUSION

The vulnerability map generated by the GIS using DRASTIC parameters acquired from the geophysical, hydrogeological, and geological field data that were obtained from the study area shows that the aquifer that underlies the study area has heterogeneous sensitivity to contaminants infiltration into the aquifer in the area. The sensitivity of the area was cumulatively determined by the seven DRASTIC parameters by inputting them into the DRASTIC model to determine the vulnerability index of the area. It was also found that, the net recharge is high, but vulnerability was found to be moderate. The pH, TDS, Fe and Mn concentration in groundwater, surface water sample 3 & 4. GIS application of the DRASTIC model was

found to be a suitable method for analyzing the groundwater vulnerability in the study area since it correlated well with the conventional geochemical analysis used for water quality.

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